

D5.3. Report on the engagement of industrial users to the SLICES-RI

Acronym	SLICES-SC
Project Title	Scientific Large-scale Infrastructure for Computing/Communication Experimental Studies – Starting Community
Grant Agreement	101008468
Project Duration	42 Months (01/03/2021 – 31/08/2024)
Due Date	30 June 2024 (M40)
Submission Date	26 June 2024 (M40)
Authors	Bartosz Belter (PSNC), Konstantinos Filis (OTE), Serge Fdida (SU)
Reviewers	Emilie Mespoulhes (SU), Cédric Crettaz (MI)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101008468. The information, documentation and figures available in this deliverable, is written by the SLICES-SC project consortium and does not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

Executive Summary

The objective of this document is to report feedback received from the Industrial Advisory Board (IAB) on SLICES-RI developments through the course of SLICES-SC. The document includes the procedures engaged to establish the IAB. It also describes the meeting held on-line to report the progress of development of SLICES-RI and collect feedback from the IAB Members. The document concludes with key takeouts and recommendations given by the IAB to SLICES-RI Consortium.

Table of Contents

TABLE OF CONTENTS	3
1. INTRODUCTION.....	4
2. PROCEDURE TO FORM THE INDUSTRIAL ADVISORY BOARD.....	4
3. THE 1ST MEETING WITH THE IAB.....	5
4. THE 2ND MEETING WITH THE IAB	7
5. CONCLUSION	10
ANNEX 1 – TEMPLATE OF NON-DISCLOSURE AGREEMENT FOR IAB MEMBERS.....	12
ANNEX 2 – SLICES-RI INDUSTRIAL ADVISORY BOARD – TERMS OF REFERENCE	16

1. Introduction

The SLICES Research Infrastructure is currently being built by the scientific community for the scientific community. However, the target group of users of the SLICES-RI is intentionally extended towards industry, including SMEs. Collaboration with industrial partners brings mutual benefits for both sides, allowing companies to develop their new solutions/technologies and services at the same time strengthening the service portfolio of SLICES. In addition, it is of utmost importance for ESFRI to demonstrate the value of scientific instruments for industry, adding an industrial and economic value to its impact assessment.

For that purpose, SLICES has developed a methodology to reach out to industrial players but organizing liaisons and also being involved in collaborative projects. This is illustrated for instance by our “Beyond 5G” BluePrint where we are part of the European 6G SNS initiative, participate to various joint projects in the 6G IA framework (6G-SUNRISE, 6G-EXCEL) and also contribute to discussions, workshops and panels with industry. The SLICES Industrial Advisory Board (IAB) complements our action by establishing a more sustained relationship with committed stakeholders.

This deliverable describes collaboration established in SLICES-SC with industry through the Industrial Advisory Board (IAB). The deliverable provides information on how the IAB has been established using procedures developed by the project. It also elaborates the outcomes of the two meetings organized to collect feedback from the IAB on SLICES-RI developments and planning.

2. Procedure to form the Industrial Advisory Board

The work on procedures to establish the Industrial Advisory Board has been started in 2022. Bartosz Belter from Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center was selected as the leader of the SLICES-SC team working towards establishment of the IAB and coordinating project efforts. In the first round of internal discussions the representatives of the following companies have been proposed as the Members of the IAB:

- ID Quantique,
- INTEL Germany,
- ERICSON,
- BISDN,
- Nextworks,
- TIM,
- PLUX Biosignals,
- iPronics,
- Telecom Italia,
- Keysight Technologies Belgium,
- Citrix,
- Verizon.

After bilateral discussions between representatives of the project and individual experts, the final group of industrial experts have been formed early 2023 with the following experts involved:

Expert	Company	Email	Gender
Valerio Frascolla	INTEL Germany	valerio.frascolla@intel.com	M
Hagen Woesner	BISDN	hagen.woesner@bisdn.de	M
Nicola Ciulli	Nextworks	n.ciulli@nextworks.it	M
Mauro Boldi	TIM	mauro.boldi@telecomitalia.it	M
Rita Cristovao	PLUX Biosignals	rcristovao@plux.info	F
Ana Gonzalez	iPronics	ana.gonzalez@ipronics.com	F
Michael Dieudonne	Keysight Technologies Belgium	michael dieudonne@keysight.com	M
Eleni Trouva	Citrix	eleni.trouva@citrix.com	F
Nirlay Kundu	Verizon	nirlay@hotmail.com	M
Pejman Panahi	ID Quantique	pejman.panahi@idquantique.com	M

Each member of the IAB signed Non-Disclosure Agreement with Sorbonne University, acting as the coordinator of SLICES-SC and representing the three projects from the SLICES family: SLICES-SC, SLICES-DS and SLICES-PP. The template of the NDA is included in this deliverable as Annex 1.

The communication channel from the project towards the IAB has been established as a dedicated mailing list with the address slices-iab@npafi.org.

3. The 1st meeting with the IAB

Time, date and the venue

- 17 May 2023, 10 AM CEST
- <https://nordunet.zoom.us/j/68377448990>

Goals of the meeting

- Introduce SLICES-RI to the members of the Industrial Advisory Board
- Present recent activities (research services & training services)
- Collect initial feedback from the IAB

The agenda

- (15 min.) Introduction to the meeting – Bartosz Belter, PSNC
- (15 min.) Introduction to SLICES – Serge Fdida, SU
- (30 min.) The first roll-out of SLICES research services – the 5G Blueprint Architecture – Damien Saucez, INRIA
- (30 min.) Training services: SLICES Academy & SLICES Mobility Programme – Carmen Guerrero, UC3M
- (30 min.) Initial feedback from the IAB, remarks, recommendations – moderated discussion
Bartosz Belter, PSNC
- Closing the meeting

Participants

- Nicola Ciulli Nextworks
- Michael Dieudonne Keysight Technologies Belgium
- Valerio Frascolla INTEL Germany
- Ana Gonzalez iPronics
- Pejman Panahi ID Quantique
- Hagen Woesner BISDN

Key takeaways from the meeting

One of the key aspects raised at the meeting was related to the concept of Open Data. The IAB members were interesting if there is a model existing worldwide to describe Open Data. It is a fact, that there is a minor progress on this field, but there is a push from the European Commission on ESFRI projects to implement Fair Data and Reproducibility. It was highlighted during the meeting that potential contribution of SLICES towards Industry could be to provide an access to large data sets for industrial partners, as there is a strong need there and many companies and SMEs could strongly benefit and improve or even design new services based on the analysis of open data available in the research community.

The IAB members were impressed by the scope of work targeted in SLICES and by the time-line. The IAB appreciated the fact that although networking seems to be key driver for SLICES, there are other technologies SLICES leverage on (e.g. Cloud-Edge Computing and IoT).

With regards to networking technologies, in particular advancements in 5G and beyond 5G, the IAB expressed their interest in the work carried out in SLICES. The questions on collaboration with other initiatives have been raised, e.g. it was recommended to explore opportunities to synchronize developments with GAIA-X on architectural aspects. Moreover, the recommendation was given on synergies with existing open facilities, like those provided by the previous EU-funded projects, like 5GENESIS or 5G-VINNI, and the new projects like 6G-XR or 6G-SANDBOX.

The discussion with the IAB also went into more technical aspects of implementation carried out in SLICES. Special attention was put on the level of use of Open-Source platforms in SLICES, but also on integration with physical equipment and North Bound interfaces towards them. The IAB also appreciated the fact of involving multiple sites in a single experiment by setting up the plan to engage GÉANT and their connectivity services to implement interconnectivity between different sites participating to SLICES.

An interesting point of the discussion was related to synergies with Industry and engaging Industry in the work within SLICES. The question for consideration was raised if and to what extent Industry is ready to join such a huge effort. However, it was made clear by SLICES representatives, that as long as we appreciate any contribution of industrial partners to SLICES, we would like to see Industry using our testbeds and that's our priority.

The IAB also identified potential types of industrial users in SLICES:

- Interested in R&D&I objectives (comparable to scientists from universities) – most probably coming from big industry with their own budget;
- Users providing Verticals (vertical technology) – e.g. new drone testing in a wireless environment – all industry, from SMEs to big Industry.

The recommendation was given on bringing clear business models for the two types of users described above.

4. The 2nd meeting with the IAB

Time, date and the venue

- 22 April 2024, 2 PM CEST
- <https://nordunet.zoom.us/j/69556849042>

Goals of the meeting

- Present recent activities in the project
- Collect feedback

Participants

- Nicola Ciulli Nextworks
- Valerio Frascolla INTEL Germany
- Ana Gonzalez iPronics
- Hagen Woesner BISDN
- Nirlay Kundu Verizon

Agenda

- Introduction – Serge Fdida, Bartosz Belter (15 min)
- SLICES Blueprint (45 min)
 - 5G – Damien Saucez
 - Cloud-Edge – Paolo Bellavista
 - Data Management Infrastructure – Yuri Demchenko
 - SLICES Academy – target skill sets from the industrial perspective - Carmen Guerrero (15 min)
- Q&A Session – Ari Pottu (45 min)

Meeting notes

The project has been introduced by Serge Fdida, the SLICES-SC coordinator and Bartosz Belter. It was highlighted:

1. The SLICES-RI is in the process of inclusion of a new Member State – Ireland, and currently there are 16 Member States (SLICES Nodes) involved.
2. The year 2024 is a very important for SLICES-RI because of closing SLICES-SC and moving to the pre-operation phase.
3. In September SLICES-RI enters the pre-operation phase, when the first research services will be offered to researchers and scientists.

The first set of presentations concerned the technical progress made by SLICES-RI and the outlook into SLICES Blueprints.

Damien Saucez presented the 5G Blueprint. The members of IAB commented or recommended the following:

1. While the presentation refers to the post-5G systems, it does not actually reflect any post-5G components in the high-level architecture. It is recommended to update the architecture with elements, which clearly indicate post-5G features (e.g. satellite connections or AI inclusion into the 5G architecture).

2. What are the commercial solutions available as part of 5G Blueprint? It is recommended to engage with industrial providers and check if they can provide in-kind contributions or discounts to complement services available currently in your testbeds.
3. It is well received that SLICES presents variety in terms of spectrum and frequencies available in the research infrastructure (available as local sites' contribution to the project). This is also well complemented with anechoic chambers to make more choices available for potential users of the infrastructure.

Paolo Bellavista presented the Edge-Cloud Blueprint. The members of IAB commented or recommended the following:

1. Similarly to the 5G Blueprint presentation, Edge-Cloud Blueprint is positioned as a post-5G system, however it uses current technologies, which is not coherent. Be conscious on the way you introduce the Blueprint: use the right terminology, mention ORAN, etc. Another recommendation on this topic was given: to avoid confusion or misinterpretation introduce the term "abstract architecture" instead of "post-5G architecture".
2. It was suggested to mention that the Edge-Cloud Blueprint is based on the dataspace concept and it's linked to your efforts on Data Management.
3. It is recommended to learn about the Destination Earth project (<https://destination-earth.eu/>)? Some of the expected outcomes of this project may be useful for SLICES (e.g. in the context of data streaming, cyber-security, etc.).
4. It was well received how the blueprint is planned for public demonstrations (Summer School in Lipari in July 2024).
5. Valerio Frascolla offered his help with the programme and offered a keynote at the Summer School).

Yuri Demchenko presented SLICES-RI Data Management Infrastructure. The members of IAB commented or recommended the following:

1. While the overall approach for Data Management in SLICES is very well articulated, regulatory aspects are missing. There are some standards you definitely comply with, please mention them on your slides. It is good to implement it in the framework of projects, but it seems SLICES-RI may be interested to have standards applying beyond the project lifetime.
2. It was suggested that SLICES-RI should be linked with TNO, as they are close to the NL members of SLICES and heavily involved in standardization.
3. It was acknowledged that SLICES-RI may provide open access to SMEs to large data sets.
4. Moreover, to attract more SMEs, SLICES-RI will need to do more than just providing open access. For SMEs it is important what are the incentives and added value. As there are other initiatives providing access to data for SMEs, SLICES-RI should find its way to be attractive sufficiently to get their attention (e.g. cascade funding).

Carmen Guerrero presented SLICES Academy and target skill sets from the industrial perspective. The presentation was well received with no further recommendations.

Ari Pouttu chaired the Q&A session, where members of the IAB were challenged with key questions concerning industrial involvement and cooperation with SLICES.

Initial feedback was collected during the meeting; however, it was decided by the IAB members to continue the discussion off-line with tools provided by the project:

- Dissemination channels to SMEs and Industry: there are many channels to disseminate to SMEs. The project should select the channels to work with and engage in the discussion.
- The cascade funding will be a significant incentive for SMEs to participate.

Screenshots from the meeting

5. Conclusion

During the SLICES-SC project course two meetings with the IAB Members have been organized. Considering the involvement of the experts in their day-to-day duties in companies they are working, the meetings were well represented by the IAB Members: 60% of the members of the IAB attended the first meeting, while 50% attended the second meeting.

Both IAB meetings went smoothly, involving discussions and feedback from the very beginning. A number of recommendations were given to the project, highlighting the areas in which the project could improve in the future. In order to track the recommendations, the table below presents them in more structured way.

Rec. 1	Potential contribution of SLICES towards Industry could be to provide an access to large data sets for industrial partners, as there is a strong need there and many companies and SMEs could strongly benefit and improve or even design new services based on the analysis of open data available in the research community.
Rec. 2	The IAB appreciated the fact that although networking seems to be key driver for SLICES, there are other technologies SLICES leverage on (e.g. Cloud-Edge Computing and IoT).
Rec. 3	A recommendation to explore opportunities to synchronize developments with GAIA-X on architectural aspects, as well as to analyze potential synergies with EU-funded facilities, e.g. 5GENESIS, 5G-VINNI, 6G-XR or 6G-SANDBOX.
Rec. 4	The IAB identified two potential types of industrial users in SLICES: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Interested in R&D&I objectives (comparable to scientists from universities) – most probably coming from big industry with their own budget;• Users providing Verticals (vertical technology) – e.g. new drone testing in a wireless environment – all industry, from SMEs to big Industry. The recommendation was given on bringing clear business models for the two types of users described above.
Rec. 5	While the 5G Blueprint presentation refers to the post-5G systems, it does not actually reflect any post-5G components in the high-level architecture. It is recommended to update the architecture with elements, which clearly indicate post-5G features (e.g. satellite connections or AI inclusion into the 5G architecture).
Rec. 6	It is recommended to engage with industrial providers and check if they can provide in-kind contributions or discounts to complement services available currently in your testbeds.
Rec. 7	Similarly to the 5G Blueprint presentation, Edge-Cloud Blueprint is positioned as a post-5G system, however it uses current technologies, which is not coherent.
Rec. 8	To avoid confusion or misinterpretation introduce the term “abstract architecture” instead of “post-5G architecture”.
Rec. 9	A suggestion to mention that the Edge-Cloud Blueprint is based on the dataspace space concept and it is linked to efforts on Data Management.

Rec. 10	While the overall approach for Data Management in SLICES is very well articulated, regulatory aspects are missing.
Rec. 11	It was suggested that SLICES-RI should be linked with TNO, as they are close to the NL members of SLICES and heavily involved in standardization.
Rec. 12	Dissemination channels to SMEs and Industry: there are many channels to disseminate to SMEs. The project should select the channels to work with and engage in the discussion.
Rec. 13	The cascade funding will be a significant incentive for SMEs to participate.

The recommendations given by the IAB will be a subject of further investigation as part of the SLICES-RI as a whole, in particular within the SLICES-PP project.

As the result of discussions between partners involved in SLICES-SC and SLICES-PP it was recommended, that the cooperation with industry through the IAB initiated in SLICES-SC will be continued within SLICES-PP as part of the work carried out on liaison with industry.

Annex 1 – Template of Non-Disclosure Agreement for IAB Members

NON-DISCLOSURE AGREEMENT

**Industrial Advisory Board of the SLICES initiative through the
SLICES-DS, SLICES-SC and SLICES-PP projects**

Sorbonne Université (“SU”) and the organisations listed on the website <http://slices-ri.eu/> have launched since 2017 the SLICES initiative to design and set up the SLICES Research Infrastructure, including the submission of the SLICES proposal to the ESFRI Roadmap 2021. SLICES is in the ESFRI Roadmap since December 2021. In this framework, SU and the organisations shown in the Attachment to this Agreement (the “Consortia”) are participating in the projects entitled (the “Projects”):

- "Scientific Large-scale Infrastructure for Computing/Communication Experimental Studies – Design Study" with the acronym "SLICES-DS", a collaborative project funded by the European Commission and effective as from 1 September 2020, for a duration of 24 months (Grant Agreement number 951850).
- "Scientific Large-scale Infrastructure for Computing/Communication Experimental Studies – Starting Community" with the acronym "SLICES-SC", a collaborative project funded by the European Commission and effective as from 1 March 2021, for a duration of 36 months (Grant Agreement, project number 101008468).
- "Scientific Large-scale Infrastructure for Computing/Communication Experimental Studies – Preparatory Phase" with the acronym "SLICES-PP", a collaborative project funded by the European Commission and effective as from 1 September 2022, for a duration of 40 months (Grant Agreement, project number 101079774).

The Consortia welcomes you as a member of the Industrial Advisory Board (“IAB”) of SLICES-DS, SLICES-SC and SLICES-PP, as projects target the same objective of paving the way for the SLICES-RI and will thus be organized in conjunction and with a single common Industrial Advisory Board.

Participation as a member of the IAB will involve you receiving, and/or participating in Projects discussions/presentations concerning information, produced and/or acquired by the Consortia members, of a proprietary or confidential nature hereafter referred to and defined as Confidential Information. In this agreement, any information disclosed to you in connection with the above-mentioned Projects and which has been explicitly marked as "Confidential" at the time of disclosure is referred to as “Confidential Information” and the Consortia member owning or holding rights to such Confidential Information, who shall be entitled to enforce the obligations contained herein, shall be referred to as the “Discloser”. To avoid doubt, the Consortia have approved the use of this agreement.

By signing below, you agree to the following:

1. to take all reasonable steps to ensure that all Confidential Information disclosed to you as a member of the IAB remains confidential during the Projects and for a period of four (4) years after the end date of the Projects (end dates to be confirmed by SU);
2. not to become involved in any commercial, manufacturing, scientific, literary or any other exploitation of the Confidential Information, whether alone or in conjunction with another party (by licence or otherwise), or use Confidential Information otherwise than for undertaking your duties as a member of the IAB without the written consent of the Discloser;
3. not to disclose the Confidential Information either directly or indirectly to any third party without the written consent of the Discloser.

In addition, you and the Consortia agree that the above obligations of confidentiality and non-use shall not apply in the following circumstances:

- a) when any such Confidential Information is public knowledge through previous publication, or when following disclosure to you as a member of the IAB, becomes general or public knowledge either through no fault of yourself or following further written agreement between you and the Discloser;
- b) when any such Confidential Information can be shown by yourself to have been in your possession prior to disclosure under this agreement, except when such Confidential Information was supplied by the staff, students or agents of the Discloser;
- c) when any such Confidential Information is received by yourself from a third party that you reasonably believe has no similar obligation of confidentiality to the Discloser;
- d) when you can reasonably demonstrate that any such information has been previously developed by yourself without reference to, or without prior benefit of, the Confidential Information or was required to be disclosed in order to comply with applicable laws or statutory regulations or with a court or administrative order.

This Agreement shall be governed by and shall be interpreted in accordance with the laws of Belgium.

In consideration of the invitation to participate as a member of the IAB, I accept the conditions set out within this agreement.

Name Surname

Title:

Date:

Signature:

SORBONNE UNIVERSITE

by Nathalie DRACH-TEMAM

Title President

Date:

Signature:

Attachment: The Consortia

□ List of SLICES-DS consortium:

SORBONNE UNIVERSITE (SU)
INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE EN INFORMATIQUE ET AUTOMATIQUE (INRIA)
PANEPISTIMIO THESSALIAS (UTH)
MANDAT INTERNATIONAL ALIAS FONDATION POUR LA COOPERATION INTERNATIONALE (MI)
INSTYTUT CHEMII BIOORGANICZNEJ POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK (PSNC)
UNIVERSIDAD CARLOS III DE MADRID (UC3M)
UCLAN CYPRUS LIMITED (UCLan)
CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE (CNR)
INTERUNIVERSITAIR MICROELECTRONICA CENTRUM (IMEC)
UNIVERSITEIT VAN AMSTERDAM (UvA)

□ List of SLICES-SC consortium:

SORBONNE UNIVERSITE (SU)
PANEPISTIMIO THESSALIAS (UTH)
MANDAT INTERNATIONAL ALIAS FONDATION POUR LA COOPERATION INTERNATIONALE (MI)
INSTYTUT CHEMII BIOORGANICZNEJ POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK (PSNC)
FUNDACIÓN IMDEA NETWORKS (IMDEA)
CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE (CNR)
EURECOM (EURECOM)
COSMOTE KINITES TILEPIKOINONIES AE (COSMOTE)
IOT LAB (IoT Lab)
OULUN YLIOPISTO (OULU)
INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE EN INFORMATIQUE ET AUTOMATIQUE (INRIA)
INTERUNIVERSITAIR MICROELECTRONICA CENTRUM (IMEC)
SZAMITASTECHNIKAI ES AUTOMATIZALASI KUTATOINTEZET (SZTAKI)
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT MÜNCHEN (TUM)

□ List of SLICES-PP consortium:

INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE EN INFORMATIQUE ET AUTOMATIQUE (INRIA)
SORBONNE UNIVERSITE (SU)
UNIVERSITEIT VAN AMSTERDAM (UvA)
PANEPISTIMIO THESSALIAS (UTH)
CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE (CNR)
INSTYTUT CHEMII BIOORGANICZNEJ POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK (PSNC)
UNIVERSIDAD CARLOS III DE MADRID (UC3M)
INTERUNIVERSITAIR MICROELECTRONICA CENTRUM (IMEC)

UCLAN CYPRUS LIMITED (UCLan)

EURECOM (EURECOM)

SZAMITASTECHNIKAI ES AUTOMATIZALASI KUTATOINTEZET (SZTAKI)

CONSORZIO INTERUNIVERSITARIO NAZIONALE PER L'INFORMATICA (CINI)

CONSORZIO NAZIONALE INTERUNIVERSITARIO PER LE TELECOMUNICAZIONI (CNT)

UNIVERSITE DU LUXEMBOURG (uni.lu)

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT MÜNCHEN (TUM)

UNIVERSIDAD DEL PAIS VASCO/ EUSKAL HERRIKO UNIBERTSITATEA (UPV/EHU)

KUNGLIGA TEKNISKA HOEGSKOLAN (KTH)

OULUN YLIOPISTO (OULU)

EBOS TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED (eBOS)

SIMULA RESEARCH LABORATORY AS (SIMULA)

CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS (CNRS)

INSTITUT MINES-TELECOM (IMT)

MANDAT INTERNATIONAL ALIAS FONDATION POUR LA COOPERATION INTERNATIONALE (MI)

IOT LAB (IoT Lab)

UNIVERSITE DE GENEVE (UniGe)

Annex 2 – SLICES-RI Industrial Advisory Board – Terms of Reference

slices
SC

Scientific
Large-scale
Infrastructure
for Computing
Communication
Experimental
Studies
Starting
Communities

SLICES-RI Industrial Advisory Board Terms of Reference

1. Background and context

 SLICES Research Infrastructure (SLICES-RI) is a flexible platform designed to support large-scale, experimental research focused on networking protocols, radio technologies, services, data collection, parallel and distributed computing and in particular cloud and edge-based computing architectures and services.

SLICES-RI consortium gathers partners from 15 European countries, all of them having committed to contribute resources and has received the endorsements of key stakeholders and the political supports of 12 European Governments. Several of the current partners are operating facilities that are already on their national and regional RI roadmaps. It is the case for instance for France, Greece, Poland, Norway and Italy. The numerous letters of support testify the strong support from the community as well as from industry and member states. SLICES-RI will encourage and foster all the initiatives from the consortium at different levels (European, national, and regional) for the inclusion of SLICES-RI in their respective roadmaps, and for participation of our community to national and European projects. Discussions and negotiations have already started in several countries involved in the SLICES-RI with their respective ministries in order to broaden the SLICES-RI consortium.

SLICES-RI ambition is to provide a unique, first-class, European wide test-platform, providing advanced compute, storage and network components, interconnected by high-speed dedicated links. SLICES will allow researchers and industry stakeholders to question scientific challenges regarding the future technologies and services. The capacity and coverage of SLICES-RI will allow (in addition to research activities) to successfully implement collaboration programs with industry and innovative SMEs.

 In SLICES-SC, we aspire to foster the community of researchers around SLICES-RI ecosystem, create and strengthen necessary links with relevant industrial stakeholders for the exploitation of the infrastructure, advance existing methods for research reproducibility and experiment repeatability, and design and deploy the necessary solutions for providing SLICES-RI with an easy to access scheme for users from different disciplines. A set of detailed research activities has been designed to materialize these efforts in tools for providing transnational (remote and physical) access to the facility, as well as virtual access to the data produced over the facilities. The respective networking activities of the project aspire in fostering the community around these infrastructures, as well as open up to new disciplines and industrial stakeholders.

2. Purpose

The Industrial Advisory Board (IAB) provides a forum to establish dialogue with business and industry in relation to the vision and mission of SLICES.

The primary function of the Industrial Advisory Board in SLICES-RI is to assist and advise the project in the following areas:

www.slices-sc.eu

- Industry trends and technology roadmaps
- Industrial needs and requirements for digital research infrastructures
- Strategic guidance to improve short- and long-term collaboration between science and industry
- Evaluation of services offered by the research infrastructure

3. Membership

Members of the IAB represent the world-wide leading manufacturers, service and solution providers and telecom operators from the broadly understood ICT sector.

4. Meetings

The Industrial Advisory Board will meet up to one time annually, typically during the events collocated with the project meetings. Meetings may be conducted face-to-face or virtual.

Any background information, including project deliverables and relevant papers will be provided up to two weeks before a scheduled meeting.

Minutes from the IAB meetings will be taken by a dedicated person from the project and circulated to the IAB members within 10 working days for their approval.

Reimbursement of travel and accommodation expenses for attending the annual face-to-face meeting can be provided upon request, and only if booked according to SLICES-SC travel rules.

5. Confidentiality

Members of the IAB shall respect the confidential character of the work conducted for the project.

Members of the IAB shall sign a Non-Disclosure Agreement to be provided to the Project Office at Sorbonne University.

